

Imidochlorides from Some Aryl Amides of 2- and 4-Methoxybenzoic Acids and their Condensation with Resorcinol

Synthesis of 2,4-Dihydroxy-2' and 4'-methoxybenzophenones

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Imidochlorides have been prepared from some aryl amides of 2- and 4-methoxybenzoic acids by the action of PCl_5 using petroleum ether (80-100°) as the solvent. These imidochlorides on condensing with resorcinol in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride furnish the respective keto-anils. The keto-anils obtained from 2-methoxybenz-aryl imidochloride on alkaline hydrolysis furnish 2,4-dihydroxy-2'-methoxybenzophenone and those obtained from 4-methoxybenz-aryl imidochlorides yield 2,4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzophenone.

The only imidochlorides derived from aryl amides of aromatic acids with methoxy substituent that are known in literature are those of anilide and *p*-anisidide of 4-methoxybenzoic acid¹. In the present investigation the imidochlorides from some aryl amides, viz., anilide, *o*-toluidide, *p*-anisidide, and *p*-phenetidide of 2- and 4-methoxybenzoic acids have been prepared and their condensations with resorcinol in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride have been studied.

The imidochlorides have been prepared by treating the amides with phosphorus pentachloride using petroleum ether of boiling range 80-100° as the solvent. It is interesting to note that no solvent had so far been used in the preparation of imidochlorides. The use of solvent had a definite advantage as the reactions took place more smoothly with little byproducts and especially so in the preparation of imidochloride from aryl amides of 2-methoxybenzoic acid, where formation of imidochloride with the solvent took place readily with little byproducts; in absence of the solvent a lot of phosphorus complex formed from which no imidochloride, even in crude form, could be obtained. The aryl amides of 4-methoxybenzoic acid also reacted more smoothly when solvent was used, affording very good yields of pure imidochloride.

A: P = H; P' = OMe. B: P = OMe; P' = H.

a: R = H; R' = H. b: R = Me; R' = H. c: R = H; R' = OMe. d: R = H; R' = OEt.

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1. Seka and Fuchs *Monatsh.*, 1931, 57, 52; Shah and Kulkarni, *this Journal*, 1950, 27, 1K.

The imidochlorides (I) condensed readily with resorcinol in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, furnishing the respective keto-anils* (II). The keto-anils (IIA), obtained from 2-methoxybenz-aryl imidochlorides (IA), on alkaline hydrolysis gave 2,4-dihydroxy-2'-methoxybenzophenone (IIIA) and those (IIB), obtained from 4-methoxybenz-aryl imidochloride (IB), furnished 2,4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzophenone (IIIB).

EXPERIMENTAL

Aryl Amides.—Anilide, *o*-toluidide, *p*-anisidide, and *p*-phenetidide of 2- and 4-methoxybenzoic acids were prepared from 2- and 4-methoxybenzoyl chlorides by following a slightly different process from that reported by Phatak and Jadhav³ who used pyridine as the solvent. The present authors find that pyridine serve no special purpose and the yields (nearly 70%) superior to that quoted by them are obtained by the following procedure.

To the ice-cold solution of the requisite amine (4*M*, e.g., aniline 21 g.) in dry benzene (200 ml) crude acid chloride (1*M*, 10 g.) was added slowly and the mixture was left overnight. The solid obtained after removing benzene was washed with HCl (dil.) and then with sodium bicarbonate solution. It was crystallised from appropriate solvent². Melting points obtained are the same as reported by Phatak and Jadhav³.

Imidochlorides (I).—PCl₅ (10 g.) was added to the suspension of aryl amide (10 g.) in petroleum ether (b.p. 80-120°, 150 ml) and the reaction mixture, protected from moisture, was refluxed on a water bath for about 1½ hrs. POCl₃ (formed during the reaction) and petroleum ether were removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The residual substance was crystallised from petroleum ether, wherever possible, or used as such by washing it with cold petroleum ether (Tables I and II).

TABLE I

Imidochlorides from aryl amides of 2-methoxybenzoic acid and corresponding keto-anils.

M=2-methoxybenz-. I=imidochloride. C=2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-2'-methoxyphenyl-.

†Imidochlorides.	**Keto-anils.	*Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1. M-anilide I IA(a)	C-keto anil	Rectangular plates	256-51°	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	4.75	4.38
2. M- <i>o</i> -toluidide I IA(b)	C-keto-2''-methyl-anil	Thick plates	321-22°	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₃ N	3.88	4.20
3. M- <i>p</i> -anisidide I IA(c)	C-keto-4''-methoxy-anil.	Fine needles	225-36°	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	3.79	4.01
4. M- <i>p</i> -phenetidide I IA(d)	C-keto-4''-ethoxy-anil	Thick cubic plates	300-201°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	3.94	3.85

†Obtained as thick oils which did not solidify. Attempts to crystallise them met with failures. These decomposed during distillation under reduced pressure. Crude oil, as such, was used for the reactions.

**Solutions of all keto-anils give brown coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

*Crystallised from absolute ethanol.

2. Phad² and Shah, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 349.

3. *Ibid.*, 1958, 35, 717.

TABLE II

Imidochlorides from aryl amides of 4-methoxybenzoic acid and the corresponding keto-amis.

N=4-methoxy benz.; I=imidochloride. D=2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-4'-methoxyphenyl-

S.No.	Imido-chlorides.†	Remarks.	‡Keto-amil.	Shape of crystals.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found.	%Nitrogen. Reqd.	Yield from 10 g. of the imidochloride.	Coloration
1.	**N-anilide I IB (s)	It separated as an oil; solidified on cooling. It crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 69-70°; yield 9 g.	D-keto-anil.	Needles	215-16°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	4.58	4.38	5 g.	Brown
2.	N- <i>o</i> -toluidide I IB(b)	It separated as an oil. It did not solidify and decomposed during distillation under reduced pressure. Crude oil was used as such for the reactions.	D-keto-4'-methyl-anil	Rectangular plates	155-56°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N	4.18	4.20	2 g. (from the imidochloride obtained from 10g. of the amide)	Dark red
3.	**N- <i>p</i> -anisidide I IB(o)	It separated as an oil; solidified on cooling. It crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 107-108°; yield 10 g.	D-keto-4'-methoxy-anil	Thin plates	213-14°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N	3.75	4.01	*2g.	Dark red
4.	N- <i>p</i> -phenanilide I IB(d)	Solid. It crystallised from petroleum ether as fine needles. It decomposed slowly; yield 10 g.	D-keto-4'-ethoxy-anil	Fine needles	205-206°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	3.40	3.80	2 g.	Brown

†Yields quoted are from 10 g. of the corresponding amide.

*The crude reaction product was found to contain lot of 4-methoxybenz-*p*-anisidide which was separated by triturating it with ether. The amide remained insoluble and the ether-soluble portion was mostly keto-anil.

‡Crystallised from absolute ethanol; No. 2, from dilute ethanol and No. 4, from benzene.

**Known. Literature gives same melting points (Saks and Fuehrer).

Keto-anils (II): Condensation of Resorcinol with Imidochlorides in presence of Anhydrous Aluminium Chloride

To a mixture of resorcinol (9g., 2*M*) and imidochloride (~1*M*, 10 g.) in dry ether (50ml), protected from moisture, an ethereal solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (8g. in 50ml, 1.5*M*) was added dropwise with constant shaking. The mixture, which turned dark red, was kept overnight at room temperature. The residue obtained after removal of the ether was decomposed by adding ice and HCl when the product usually separated in a pasty form. On washing it with water several times, a yellow solid was obtained which was crystallised from an appropriate solvent (Tables I and II).

2,4-Dihydroxy-2'-methoxybenzophenone (IIIA).—KOH (2g.) was added to any of the keto-anils of IIA series [*i.e.* IIA (a) or IIA(b) or IIA (c) or IIA (d), (1g.)], dissolved in absolute ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for about 8 hours. Residue obtained after distilling the solvent was dissolved in water, acidified with HCl, and the solid separating was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 247-48°. (Found: C, 68.98; H, 5.00. C₁₄H₁₂O₄ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.91%). It developed a reddish brown colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

Keto-anils IIA(a), IIA(b), IIA(c), IIA(d) furnished the same product (IIIA) on hydrolysis.

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (IIIA) was prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solution of benzophenone (IIIA) (0.5 g. in 2ml EtOH) with 1% ethanolic solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (10 ml) for about 8 hours. It crystallised from absolute ethanol in needles, m.p. 282-83°. (Found: N, 13.22. C₂₀H₁₆O₇N₄ requires N, 13.20%).

2,4-Dihydroxy-4'-methoxybenzophenone (IIIB).—Keto-anils (IIB,a) (IIB,b) (IIB, c) and (IIB, d) were hydrolysed by following the same procedure as used in the hydrolysis of keto-anils of IIA series. All these keto-anils furnished the same substance. It crystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 158-59°. (Found: C, 68.55; H, 4.54. C₁₄H₁₄O₄ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.91%). It developed a brown colour with EtOH-FeCl₃.

2, 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (IIIB) was prepared as before using benzophenone (IIIB). It crystallised from ethanol as needles, m.p. 262-63°. (Found: N, 12.87. C₂₃H₁₆O₇N₄ requires N, 13.20%).

*The quantities expressed in g. are those used in the condensation of 4-methoxybenzanilide imidochloride. Appropriate quantities of resorcinol and aluminium chloride calculated on the basis of molecular proportions were used in the condensation of other imidochlorides.

In case where crude imidochlorides were used in the condensation, their amounts were determined on the basis of the quantities of amides used in the preparation (vide Tables I and II).